

Research

The Impact of the Service Quality of Tourism Sector on The Balance of Payments

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Abstract: The main objective this paper to examine the impact of tourism expectations and perception on services provided by the world's tourism industry. Also, following specific objectives are expected to be achieved: First one to examine the world travel and tourism business whether its declining or increasing ,second one to analyses most popular destinations and least destinations for international tourists and inflows ,third one to analyses regional tourism for international tourists and inflows , fourth one to compare tourism services and merchandise trade by analysing the balance of payments for the destinations in the global and fifth one to recognize policy recommendations that improve the travel and tourism services in the world based on the empirical findings. The micro study has used in SERVQUAL model and the macro study has used UNWTO data. The overall perceived quality of service is high (1.184), which means that the level of service they receive is higher than expected. This may be because the tourism industry maintains a complete customer base. The Outcome of Macro study are Export from international tourism (USD 1.7 trillion) equal to 7% of global export or 29% of world services export. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the main goals were successfully achieved, and other specific tasks were included in the study. The SERVQUAL model is used in this research. Even so, the SERVQUAL model must be transformed in such a way that it can gather the perspectives and understandings of research and tourism. Macro study is value added to the research. Finally, even though tourism satisfaction is the focus of the micro-foundations, the addition of macro studies to this study is more significant. In the macro study western countries more dominated international tourist arrivals and international tourism receipts. Fifty nations who have less than thousands international tourists' arrivals and no proper recording international tourism receipts. This should be changed. The health tourism should be increased, and a mechanism to meet the demand of tourists for indigenous and traditional therapies other than Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani and western medicine will be focused. Tourism Security must be concerned about every nation. Therefore, the World Tourism Organization should do a proper mechanism to tourist safety.

Keywords: Tourism, Expectations, Perception, SERVQUAL and UNWTO

Introduction

Tourism is one of the significant service industries around the world. The importance of international tourism can be seen in its role in generating foreign exchange earnings. Tourism can create jobs directly through the sale of hotels, restaurants, nightclubs, taxis and souvenirs, and indirectly by the supply of ideas, goods and services needed for tourism-related ventures. The good thing about informal or unreported employment is that the money generated remains in the local economy and is used many times, which has a significant multiplier effect. It is estimated that by 2020, three times more people will be travelling abroad than in 2003 (Robinson, 2003). Most countries are aware of the tourism potential and are trying to attract more foreign tourists. This provides an opportunity to increase the export of services. International tourism is very competitive. With the right products, success still depends on marketing, oversight, and continuous improvement. Unfortunately, most countries, regions and regions have cohesive tourism strategies to address everyday situations. In developed countries, existing regulations, social and commercial infrastructure provide the administrative context for tourism, but in developing countries, this is less obvious, and tourism development is often individual developers or multinational corporations. They were driven by the short-term financial judgment of (Robinson, 2003). Therefore, tourism challenges and concerns in developed and developing countries need to be understood and analyzed separately.

According to BPM 6th (Balance of Payments and International Investment Position Manual sixth editions) Balance of Payments provides a framework applicable to a variety of economies, from the smallest and most developing economies to the more advanced and sophisticated economies. As a result, it is recognized that some items may not be relevant in all cases. Balance of Payments is a statistical description that summarizes transactions between residents and non-residents. It consists of goods and services accounts, primary income accounts, secondary income accounts, capital accounts and financial accounts. In the underlying bookkeeping system for payout balances, each transaction is made up of two entries, and the total of credit and debit entries is recorded as the same. The different accounts in the balance are distinguished according to the nature of the economic resources provided and received. So how does this study affect the balance of payments by the tourism sector? Therefore, according to the BPM 6th, Export from international tourism in particular year is equal to receipts in destinations plus passenger transport. International

tourism export revenue consists of "travel" (receipt at destination) and "passenger transport" receipt.

The main objective this paper to examine the impact of tourism expectations and perception on services provided by the world's tourism industry.

The following specific objectives are expected to be achieved:

- To examine the world travel and tourism business whether its declining or increasing
- To analyse most popular destinations and least destinations for international tourists and inflows.
- To analyse regional tourism for international tourists and inflows
- To compare tourism services and merchandise trade by analysing the balance of payments for the destinations in the global.
- To recognise policy recommendations that improve the travel and tourism services in the world based on the empirical findings.

A noteworthy feature of the paper is to examine the relationship between tourism services and the balance of payments. If tourism exports are increasing, it will have a positive impact on the balance of payments. The study is carried out worldwide and is trying to comprehensively determine the measure of service quality in the tourism industry. It is foreseen that the effects will be of immeasurable value for the business not only for tour operators in guest countries but also for managers around the world who have related sociocultural roots.

Many theoretical approaches have been used to explain the relationship between uncertainty and satisfaction. Many theories have been used to understand the process by which customers determine satisfaction (Oliver,1980). The theory can be divided into three main groups: inconsistency, fairness, and attribution (Adee,2004). Also, many theories are surrounding the satisfaction and service paradigm. The discrepancy theory suggests that consumers determine satisfaction by evaluating the actual product/service. Anderson (1973) has identified four psychological theories that can be used to explain the effects of expectation or satisfaction. Assimilation, contrast, generalized negation, and assimilation contrast. The central process of satisfaction is the comparison of product or service performance with what is expected. This process has traditionally been described as a "confirm / non-confirm" process (Vavra,1997). First, customers form expectations before they buy a product or service. Second, the consumption or experience of a product or service produces a perceived quality level that is influenced by

expectations (Oliver,1980). If the perceived performance is slightly lower than the expected performance, assimilation will occur, and the perceived performance will be adjusted to the same expected value. If the perceived performance is significantly below expectations, the contrast will occur, exaggerating the perceived lack of performance (Vavra,1997).

Performance exceeds expectations, satisfaction increases, but percentage decreases. There is further disapproval because the perceived performance is below expectations. Satisfaction depends on subjective factors (such as customer needs and emotions) and objective factors (such as product or service functionality). When applied to the hospitality industry, there have been many studies investigating the attributes that traveller considers essential regarding customer satisfaction. Service quality and customer satisfaction are clear concepts but are closely related (Ivanka, 2009). Atkinson (1988) found that cleanliness, security, cost performance, and staff courtesy determine customer satisfaction. Knutson (1988) revealed that room cleanliness and comfort, location convenience, prompt service, safety and security, and employee friendliness are essential. A study conducted by Akan (1995) found that critical factors were employee behaviour, cleanliness and timeliness. Meanwhile, a study by Choi and Chu (2001) concludes that staff quality, room quality, and value are the top three factors in hotels that determine traveller satisfaction.

Consistency theory suggests that consumers experience some tension when expectations do not match actual product performance. To alleviate this tension, consumers make adjustments, either by expectations or perceptions of the actual performance of the product. Four theoretical approaches have been pursued under the umbrella of the consistency theory. (1) Assimilation theory. (2) Contrast theory; (3) Assimilation contrast theory; (4) Negative theory (Peyton et al ,2003).

Table 1: Comparison of Various Customer Satisfaction Theories

Theory	Product/Service Experience	Effect on Perceived Product Service Performance	Moderating Conditions	Effect
Contrast	Positive confirmation Negative disconfirmation	Perceived Performance enhanced Perceived performance lowered		

Assimilation / Contrast	Small confirmation or Disconfirmation Large confirmation or Disconfirmation	Perceived performance assimilated toward expectations. Perceived performance contrasted against expectations	Purchase is ego-involved	Performance difference exaggerated
Dissonance	Negative disconfirmation	Perceived performance modified to fit with expectations	Purchase made under conditions of ambiguity	Less modification
Generalized Negativity	Either confirmation or disconfirmation	Perceived product performance lowered`	Purchase is ego involved, high commitment and interest	More modification
Hypothesis Testing	Either confirmation or disconfirmation	Perceived performance modified to fit expectations	Purchase made under conditions of ambiguity	More modification

Source: Adopted from Yc Youjic "A Critical Review of Customer Satisfaction" in Zothumt, Valore "Review of Marketing 1989, Chicago, American Marketing Association, 1991. Cited in Terry G. Vavra (1997). Improving Your Measurement of Customer Satisfaction: A Guide to Creating, Conducting, Analyzing, and Reporting Customer Satisfaction Measurement Programs. American Society for Quality.

Yoo and Park (2007) found that SERVQUAL equipment is widely applied in various service industries, including tourism and hospitality. Parasuraman, Zeithamal and Berry (1988) created a 22-item device called SERVQUAL to measure consumer perceptions of service quality. SERVQUAL addresses many elements of quality of service divided into the dimensions of tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy.

Nadiri and Hussian (2005) said that

"According to the SERVQUAL model, service quality can be measured by identifying the gaps between customers' expectations of the service to be rendered and their perceptions of the actual performance of service. SERVQUAL is based on five dimensions of service:

Tangibility: Tangibility refers to the physical characteristics associated with the service encounter. The physical surroundings represented by objects (for example, interior design) and subjects (for example, the appearance of employees).

Reliability: The service provider's ability to provide accurate and dependable services; consistently performing the service right.

Responsiveness: A firm's willingness to assist its customers by providing fast and efficient service performances; the willingness that employees exhibit to promptly and efficiently solve customer requests and problems.

Assurance: Diverse features that provide confidence to customers (such as the firm's specific service knowledge polite and trustworthy behaviour from employees).

Empathy: The service firm's readiness to provide each customer with personal service".

Whether in tourism or other industries, quality of service and customer satisfaction continues to attract the attention of both researchers and practitioners. Interest in service quality is associated with financial performance (Nelson et al., 1992; Rust & Zahorik, 1993; Rust et al., 1994), costs (Kellogg et al., 1997), and customer satisfaction (Bolton & Drew, 1991) (Boulding et al. 1993; Cronin & Taylor, 1992), customer retention (Boshoff, 1997; Hocutt, 1998; Keaveney, 1995) and price elasticity (Bolton & Myers, 2003). Customer satisfaction is becoming increasingly important as it is considered a key indicator of future earnings (Anderson & Fornell, 2000). Customer satisfaction also leads to increased customer loyalty (Anderson & Sullivan, 1993; Bearden & Teel, 1983; Oliver, 1980). Future transactions cost reductions (Reichheld & Sasser, 1990), customer satisfaction guarantees future returns by increasing loyalty (Bolton, 1998; Fornell, 1992, Rust et al., 1994), and elasticity. (Anderson, 1996) and minimize poor quality. This can lead to customer defects (Anderson & Sullivan, 1993). Satisfied customer reviews reduce the cost of attracting new customers and increase the overall reputation of the company, but dissatisfied customers naturally have the opposite effect (Anderson, 1998; Fornell, 1992). Satisfied customers are high-earning, low-risk economic assets (Fornell et al., 2006). Customer satisfaction also creates shareholder value by increasing future cash inflows and reducing volatility (Gruca & Rego, 2005).

Quality of service is described as a form associated with satisfaction but unequal attitudes resulting from comparing expectations and outcomes (Bolton & Drew, 1991; Parasuraman et al., 1988). Customer satisfaction is defined as the "customer satisfaction response". This is a determination of whether the functionality of a product or service or the product or service itself (or provides) has a satisfactory level associated with consumption, including the achievement or absence of an adequate level (Oliver, 1997). The main consensus in the literature on quality of service and customer satisfaction is that service quality and customer satisfaction are conceptually different

but closely related (Dabholkar, 1995; Parasuraman et al., 1994; Sureshchandar et al., 2002). The most common explanation for these two differences is that perceived service quality is a form of attitude and a long-term overall rating, while satisfaction is a measure specific to a particular transaction (Bitner, 1990; Bolton & Drew, 1991). Parasuraman et al., 1988). Also, service quality is only one of the precedents for customer satisfaction (Cronin & Taylor, 1994; Zeithaml et al., 2002), and there is a general agreement that the intention to purchase is less effective than customer satisfaction in service quality (Cronin & Taylor, 1992; Dabholkar et al., 2000).

One of the earliest works related to large-scale development in the field of quality of service in tourism belongs to Saleh and Ryan (1991). These authors developed a 33-point scale for analyzing the quality of service in the hospitality industry using the SERVQUAL model. The range was tested in Canada and tried to reflect the basic assumptions underlying SERVQUAL. The author selected the appropriate item/question for each of the five dimensions. Therefore, many items not controlled by SERVQUAL were excluded. Note that previous researchers found evidence that SERVQUAL incorrectly reflects the measurement of service quality in all industries (Babakus & Boller, 1992; Carman, 1990; Cronin & Taylor, 1992, 1994). Saleh and Ryan (1991) also found similar evidence in this article when independent factor analysis produced factors that differed from the SERVQUAL dimension.

According to Samuelson (1972), the tourism sector's export activities focus on citizens of the host country selling goods and services to international tourists. The credit side of the "Travel" item records the costs paid by international tourists to obtain various goods and services in the host country. In contrast, the debit side allows citizens of the source country to purchase the goods. Costs to be recorded are recorded when travelling abroad. The final result of this transaction shows the difference between the two. As such, the valuation of the tourism sector based on credit or debit surplus in the "Travel" item is not considered reliable. The net tourism income calculation gives different results because it does not include the costs incurred by the citizens of the source country, nor the costs incurred by the citizens of the host country for currency exchange that directly affects tourism income. Expenses in this category related to foreign exchange are included in the balance of payments debit via various headings, except those related to the "Travel" item. Since the tourism industry is one of the fastest-growing sectors, it has been adopted by many developed and developing countries as one of the most notable sources of economic growth, development and minimization of external debt. It has been. Tourism income has a significant

impact on the economy, resulting in job creation, additional private and public sector income, foreign currency income, higher investment and growth (De Mello, Pack, & Sinclair, 2002). Thirlwall (1979) identified the importance of the balance of payments to economic growth and needed to reduce it if the country faced a balance of payments problems in expanding demand before reaching short-term capacity growth. Said there is. The supply is never fully utilized. Investment is not recommended. Technological progress is slowing, and national goods are less desirable than foreign goods.

Materials and methods

The research strategy is quantitative. It is used in this strategy because it is appropriate to answer research questions. This strategy will allow us to adequately measure our variables derived from the SERVQUAL model and identify subtle differences between people in terms of assessing their perceptions of service quality. It will also provide us with a criterion for making these distinctions, and also provide a basis for more accurate estimates of the degree of relationship between variables. This gives the research results in high reliability and reliability. This strategy is used not only to describe the various attributes of the SERVQUAL model and their importance to customers but also why they consider these attributes vital to them. A quantitative strategy is used because the results can be summarized for the specific context in which the study is conducted. A quantitative strategy is scientific, which means that it will take into account deviations and values in order to make the results reproducible.

Figure 1 shows that conceptual framework of this study. First is microstudy. There are ten measurements that characterize service quality of a tourism sector. There are, Core-tourism experience, Information, Hospitality, Fairness of price, Hygiene, Amenities, Value for money, Logistics, Food and Security. This is general variables to understands of effect for tourism prospects and perceptions on services provided by the world's tourism industry (Burns et al. (2003) , Chadee and Matson (1996) , Chaudhary (2000) , Edward (2006) , Fuchs and Weiermair (2004) , Heung (2000) , Kozak (2001) , Kozak and Rimmington (2000) , Millan and Esteban (2004) , Otto and Ritchie (1996) , Poon and Low (2005) , Saleh and Ryan (1991) , Tribe and Snaith (1998) , Tsang and Qu (2000) and Yuksel and Yuksel (2001)).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Compiled by the author

Second one is Macro Study. According to UNWTO, there are ten measurements that characterize service quality of a tourism sector. There are International tourist number and International tourist receipts.

Micro Study - primary data sources are used to answer survey questions. Primary data is obtained primarily through surveys. Estimated surveys are conducted on 700 tourists worldwide. Nevertheless, the study has carried 735 tourists around the world.

Macro Study -The tourism trade is one of the most encouraging entrepreneurs in the world and plays a vital role in achieving critical macroeconomic goals for economic growth, employment, sustainable economy and social development. The nature of tourism is a macro study, not a micro-

study. If someone creates a survey and evaluates the results using SERVQUAL or some other method, that is not enough. Therefore, use the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) data to cross-check what is happening now. Descriptive statistics consist of techniques used to summarize and explain numerical data for ease of interpretation. Descriptive statistics summarize a set of sample observations. Marco's survey has two variables: international receipts and tourists. These data can be viewed as percentage data, shared data, and thousands or millions of data.

Micro Study - The purpose of analyzing the primary data collected during the survey is to answer some research questions, as shown in the first chapter, on how tourists evaluate the quality of service in the tourism industry and whether they are satisfied with its quality. This allows to achieve the objectives of the research, which mainly describe experimental phenomena.

Data analysis for this study was carried out in two stages, the demographic analysis and the fundamental analysis. For a demographic analysis, which mainly includes descriptive statistics to summarize the data, the demographic characteristics of the respondents were presented to simplify the understanding of the data.

The fundamental analysis included a factor analysis, the purpose of which was to determine whether SERVQUAL is applicable in the context of the tourism industry, and a gap analysis, which used descriptive statistics to summarize the means of perception and expectations tourists perception minus expectations estimates for each item and metrics are calculated to identify gaps in service quality.

The demographic profile of the respondents is: 60.27% of the respondents said they were on vacation, 9.5% were for business, others (religious) 6.94% and 6.45% for education. 7.45% of respondents said they would visit friends and relatives, 3.31% for official work, 2.56% for a conference, 2.45% for residential care and 1.07% for medical treatment. In particular, no percentage received any media and transfers. 35.24% of the respondents said this was the first tour of their life and the remaining 64.76% said they did not travel for the first time. Men account for 47.62%, and women are slightly higher than men 49.52%. 2.86% does not say the binaries were not acquired.

Most of the respondents were married. This was 47.62%, followed by single 34.29%, separated 6.67% and divorced and widowed have the same percentage. This was 5.71%. In this study, the same, but the highest of the respondents, age was recorded; it was 25.71%, age 40-49, and age 60+. 33 - 39 is recorded as 22.86%, then 30 - 39, 18.10% and 18-29, and then 7.62%. Up to 18

years old did not respond to the study. Most of the respondents were some colleges, accounting for 52.38%, followed by school graduates, 39.05%, secondary schools or less than 5.71%, and college owners were 2.86%. College students did not respond to the study. The majority of respondents (38.10%) stated that their annual income is less than \$ 25,000, followed by 20.95% who received more than \$ 75,000, 19.05% \$ 35,000–49,999. US, and 4.7% 50 000–74 999 US dollars, as well as 9.52% 25 000–34 999 US dollars according to the data.

According to Figure 2, most tourists came from China. This was 12.8%. The second place went to the USA, and it was 7.07%. 3rd place went to France, and it amounted to 5.44%. According to Figure 3, in the study of the most visited destinations in France, it was 8.98%. Spain took second place, and it amounted to 8.47%. The USA took 3rd place, and it amounted to 7.95%.

Reliability and Validity - The internal consistency of the modified SERVQUAL elements was evaluated by calculating the overall reliability scale. The overall confidence scale for the study is 0.962, which indicates an overall confidence coefficient higher than that of the Parasuraman et al., (1988) study, which was 0.92. This value of reliability for the study is significant, since the highest reliability that can be obtained is 1.0, and this indicates that the elements of the six dimensions of the SERVQUAL model are accepted for analysis. Table 3 shows the confidence scale for all six measurements and the confidence scale for each measurement. Remove each element from the measurement to see if the removed element is genuine. If the Cronbach alpha value for a dimension increases when an element is deleted, this indicates that the member is not regular in that dimension.

From table 3 above, it can be realized every item in the model showed that over higher than 0.90 value in each measurement. This confirmed that every element which used accurate and maintained the quality of internal consistency.

According to table 4, the correlation matrix applies to evaluate the strength and direction of the connection between two elements or variables. A high positive correlation value indicates that objects measure the same skill or element. If the elements do not have a high correlation, they may measure different characteristics or may not be clearly defined. The Variables among correlation values greater than 0.7 are often considered to be highly correlated.

Table 4 shows that the strong correlation from AAS 6.4 to AAS 6.6 is 0.965. The weak correlation was 0.400 from CTE 1.1 to CTE 1.7. Therefore, the correlation range of this questionnaire was 0.965-0.400.

Table 2: Demographic Statistics

Characteristics	Percentage (%)	Characteristics	Percentage (%)
Purpose of visit		Age	
Holiday	60.27%	Under 18	0.00%
Conference	2.56%	18-29	7.62%
Education	6.45%	30-39	22.86%
Official	3.31%	40-49	25.71%
Medical Treatment	1.07%	50-59	18.10%
Transit	0.00%	60 +	25.71%
Residence	2.45%	Highest level of schooling	
Media	0.00%	High school or less	5.71%
Visiting F/R	7.45%	Technical school	2.86%
Employment	0.00%	Some college	52.38%
Business	9.50%	College graduate	0.00%
Other	6.94%	Graduate school	39.05%
First tour		Annual Household Income	
No	64.76%	Under \$25,000	38.10%
Yes	35.24%	\$25,000 - \$34,999	9.52%
Gender		\$35,000 - \$49,999	19.05%
Woman	49.52%	\$50,000 - \$74,999	12.38%
Man	47.62%	\$75,000 - or more	20.95%
Non-binary	0.00%		
Prefer not to say	2.86%		
Marital Status			
Single	34.29%		
Married	47.62%		
Divorced	5.71%		
Widowed	5.71%		
Separated	6.67%		

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

Figure 2: Nationality of Tourists

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

Figure 3: Destinations of Tourists

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

Table 3: Reliability Coefficient (Cronbach's alphas)

Measurement	Number of items	Cronbach alpha for Measurement	Items	Cronbach alpha if item deleted
CTE	9	0.948	CTE 1.1	0.955
			CTE 1.2	0.940
			CTE 1.3	0.939
			CTE 1.4	0.940
			CTE 1.5	0.938
			CTE 1.6	0.937
			CTE 1.7	0.940
			CTE 1.8	0.941
			CTE 1.9	0.946
INF	6	0.951	INF 2.1	0.946
			INF 2.2	0.941
			INF 2.3	0.934
			INF 2.4	0.930
			INF 2.5	0.942
			INF 2.6	0.953
HOS	10	0.970	HOS 3.1	0.973
			HOS 3.2	0.967
			HOS 3.3	0.965
			HOS 3.4	0.966
			HOS 3.5	0.965
			HOS 3.6	0.968
			HOS 3.7	0.964
			HOS 3.8	0.965
			HOS 3.9	0.966
			HOS 3.10	0.968
FPV	11	0.971	FPV 4.1	0.971
			FPV 4.2	0.969
			FPV 4.3	0.966
			FPV 4.4	0.968
			FPV 4.5	0.968
			FPV 4.6	0.967
			FPV 4.7	0.971
			FPV 4.8	0.968
			FPV 4.9	0.966
			FPV 4.10	0.967
			FPV 4.11	0.970
HAF	10	0.972	HAF 5.1	0.970
			HAF 5.2	0.969
			HAF 5.3	0.969
			HAF 5.4	0.969
			HAF 5.5	0.969
			HAF 5.6	0.966
			HAF 5.7	0.970
			HAF 5.8	0.971
			HAF 5.9	0.972

				HAF 5.10	0.970
				AAS 6.1	0.974
				AAS 6.2	0.973
				AAS 6.3	0.974
				AAS 6.4	0.973
AAS		10	0.977	AAS 6.5	0.972
				AAS 6.6	0.972
				AAS 6.7	0.971
				AAS 6.8	0.973
				AAS 6.9	0.980
				AAS 6.10	0.979

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

Validity - Validity is a measure of the gravity or soundness of a research tool. An instrument is said to be valid if it is possible to measure what is to be measured or expected. A tool that is said to be valid if it can reveal the data of the studied variables. A quantitative research tool is often used in the form of a questionnaire. The questionnaire is a data collection technique. Answers are provided through a series of questions or a written statement. The validity of the questionnaire needs to be verified, whether it is valid or not. To evaluate the effectiveness of the questionnaire, Pearson and moment correlation using SPSS was used. Pearson's correlation from the time it is received the likelihood test is created by comparing the question mark for each item with a total score. The subject questionnaire of the subject was significantly correlated with the overall score that the subject was valid.

Table 4: Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	CTE 1.1	CTE 1.2	CTE 1.3	CTE 1.4	CTE 1.5	CTE 1.6	CTE 1.7	CTE 1.8	CTE 1.9
CTE 1.1	1								
CTE 1.2	0.758	1							
CTE 1.3	0.497	0.760	1						
CTE 1.4	0.434	0.700	0.950	1					
CTE 1.5	0.461	0.779	0.888	0.860	1				
CTE 1.6	0.481	0.734	0.818	0.796	0.839	1			
CTE 1.7	0.400	0.601	0.791	0.766	0.752	0.843	1		
CTE 1.8	0.443	0.691	0.637	0.627	0.667	0.784	0.830	1	
CTE 1.9	0.583	0.622	0.492	0.507	0.586	0.687	0.658	0.873	1
	INF 2.1	INF 2.2	INF 2.3	INF 2.4	INF 2.5	INF 2.6			
INF 2.1	1								
INF 2.2	0.815	1							
INF 2.3	0.866	0.891	1						
INF 2.4	0.768	0.848	0.919	1					

INF 2.5	0.630	0.693	0.747	0.870	1						
INF 2.6	0.590	0.546	0.629	0.737	0.893	1					
	HOS 3.1	HOS 3.2	HOS 3.3	HOS 3.4	HOS 3.5	HOS 3.6	HOS 3.7	HOS 3.8	HOS 3.9	HOS 3.10	
HOS 3.1	1										
HOS 3.2	0.819	1									
HOS 3.3	0.729	0.949	1								
HOS 3.4	0.610	0.804	0.892	1							
HOS 3.5	0.529	0.713	0.804	0.928	1						
HOS 3.6	0.500	0.674	0.746	0.815	0.909	1					
HOS 3.7	0.562	0.770	0.845	0.846	0.922	0.884	1				
HOS 3.8	0.512	0.707	0.788	0.789	0.871	0.862	0.957	1			
HOS 3.9	0.612	0.773	0.813	0.741	0.755	0.681	0.875	0.901	1		
HOS 3.10	0.603	0.701	0.727	0.680	0.687	0.633	0.775	0.833	0.947	1	
	FPV 4.1	FPV 4.2	FPV 4.3	FPV 4.4	FPV 4.5	FPV 4.6	FPV 4.7	FPV 4.8	FPV 4.9	FPV 4.10	FPV 4.11
FPV 4.1	1										
FPV 4.2	0.753	1									
FPV 4.3	0.798	0.879	1								
FPV 4.4	0.622	0.906	0.876	1							
FPV 4.5	0.604	0.676	0.837	0.791	1						
FPV 4.6	0.560	0.648	0.805	0.803	0.904	1					
FPV 4.7	0.516	0.522	0.676	0.645	0.828	0.896	1				
FPV 4.8	0.583	0.771	0.794	0.873	0.815	0.878	0.800	1			
FPV 4.9	0.719	0.815	0.846	0.847	0.836	0.850	0.736	0.902	1		
FPV 4.10	0.762	0.726	0.834	0.769	0.768	0.839	0.702	0.770	0.896	1	
FPV 4.11	0.772	0.705	0.742	0.669	0.614	0.695	0.613	0.673	0.820	0.888	1
	HAF 5.1	HAF 5.2	HAF 5.3	HAF 5.4	HAF 5.5	HAF 5.6	HAF 5.7	HAF 5.8	HAF 5.9	HAF 5.10	
HAF 5.1	1										
HAF 5.2	0.887	1									
HAF 5.3	0.845	0.905	1								
HAF 5.4	0.822	0.888	0.928	1							
HAF 5.5	0.820	0.776	0.861	0.840	1						
HAF 5.6	0.813	0.842	0.887	0.915	0.881	1					
HAF 5.7	0.684	0.698	0.764	0.783	0.722	0.856	1				
HAF 5.8	0.580	0.632	0.657	0.685	0.752	0.853	0.888	1			
HAF 5.9	0.609	0.613	0.588	0.569	0.722	0.744	0.827	0.924	1		
HAF 5.10	0.756	0.795	0.707	0.717	0.713	0.855	0.789	0.840	0.858	1	
	AAS 6.1	AAS 6.2	AAS 6.3	AAS 6.4	AAS 6.5	AAS 6.6	AAS 6.7	AAS 6.8	AAS 6.9	AAS 6.10	
AAS 6.1	1										

AAS 6.2	0.878	1								
AAS 6.3	0.818	0.850	1							
AAS 6.4	0.842	0.913	0.901	1						
AAS 6.5	0.860	0.859	0.916	0.934	1					
AAS 6.6	0.856	0.942	0.871	0.965	0.925	1				
AAS 6.7	0.882	0.893	0.895	0.903	0.947	0.945	1			
AAS 6.8	0.827	0.863	0.848	0.881	0.903	0.929	0.941	1		
AAS 6.9	0.721	0.633	0.654	0.595	0.705	0.652	0.732	0.705	1	
AAS 6.10	0.721	0.683	0.563	0.629	0.632	0.710	0.723	0.790	0.625	1

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

Based on the conclusion below, remember some values, such as the Pearson correlation or the correlation value between an element or an element with an overall score, also known as r_{xy} . Sig. (2-tailed) was a significant level of 5%, while the total number of respondents is 735 people. As explained below, it is possible to determine whether the subject questionnaire was valid or not by looking at the significance value or comparing the r_{xy} values with the r-table of the product-moment. This is interpreted as the validity of the test results for the entire element as a whole. Based on the significant value obtained by Sig. (2-tailed) $0,000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that all elements are valid. Based on the obtained counter value $r_{xy} 0.835 > r$ of the table product-moment 0.087, it can be concluded that the all element was valid.

Expectations and Perceptions - Expectation and perceptions are measured on a 7-point equivalence scale, with higher numbers indicating higher levels of expectation or perceptions. Overall, customer expectations exceed the level of service indicated by perceptions performance. This is reflected in the “gap” of the assessment (Expectation - Perceptions). According to Parasuraman et al. (1988), it is normal for customers to exceed their service expectations and always need improvement.

Table 5: Summary of means of customer' expectations and gap scores

Measurement	Items	Expectation Score	Perception Score	Gap Score
Core-tourism experience	CTE 1.1	5.829	4.981	0.848
	CTE 1.2	5.714	4.895	0.819
	CTE 1.3	5.810	4.933	0.876
	CTE 1.4	6.038	4.990	1.048
	CTE 1.5	5.990	4.990	1.000
	CTE 1.6	6.238	4.905	1.333
	CTE 1.7	6.071	4.752	1.318

	CTE 1.8	6.048	4.590	1.457
	CTE 1.9	6.257	4.686	1.571
Information	INF 2.1	6.352	4.743	1.610
	INF 2.2	5.848	4.657	1.190
	INF 2.3	5.886	4.733	1.152
	INF 2.4	5.810	4.905	0.905
	INF 2.5	5.581	4.876	0.705
	INF 2.6	5.648	4.829	0.819
Hospitality	HOS 3.1	5.886	4.552	1.333
	HOS 3.2	5.810	4.505	1.305
	HOS 3.3	6.029	4.600	1.429
	HOS 3.4	5.990	4.743	1.248
	HOS 3.5	6.133	4.810	1.324
	HOS 3.6	6.067	4.686	1.381
	HOS 3.7	6.048	4.705	1.343
	HOS 3.8	5.857	4.695	1.162
	HOS 3.9	5.876	4.581	1.295
	HOS 3.10	5.810	4.400	1.410
Fairness of price and value of money	FPV 4.1	5.648	5.000	0.648
	FPV 4.2	5.714	5.086	0.629
	FPV 4.3	5.933	5.048	0.886
	FPV 4.4	6.057	4.790	1.267
	FPV 4.5	6.057	4.743	1.314
	FPV 4.6	6.162	4.619	1.543
	FPV 4.7	6.057	4.667	1.390
	FPV 4.8	6.219	4.771	1.448
	FPV 4.9	6.133	4.895	1.238
	FPV 4.10	6.038	4.876	1.162
	FPV 4.11	5.857	4.914	0.943
Hygiene and Food	HAF 5.1	6.086	5.105	0.981
	HAF 5.2	6.000	5.181	0.819
	HAF 5.3	6.143	4.943	1.200
	HAF 5.4	6.076	5.010	1.067
	HAF 5.5	6.248	4.952	1.295
	HAF 5.6	6.190	5.000	1.190
	HAF 5.7	6.038	4.848	1.190
	HAF 5.8	6.076	5.048	1.029
	HAF 5.9	5.895	4.924	0.971
	HAF 5.10	5.990	5.190	0.800
Amenities and Security	AAS 6.1	6.362	5.086	1.276

AAS 6.2	6.171	4.905	1.267
AAS 6.3	6.419	4.933	1.486
AAS 6.4	6.095	4.781	1.314
AAS 6.5	6.333	4.867	1.467
AAS 6.6	6.181	4.895	1.286
AAS 6.7	6.324	4.962	1.362
AAS 6.8	6.505	4.781	1.724
AAS 6.9	6.095	4.895	1.200
AAS 6.10	6.390	4.886	1.505

Overall average gap scores for all 6 Measurement 1.192

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

In the initial measurement of travel experience, the highest expected result was CTE 1.9. The tourist environment was calm and peaceful, with a rating of 6.257. Subsequently, the highest score for measuring information was INF 2.1. The tourist information Centre should be at airports with a rating of 6.352. Then, HOS 3.5 was the highest rating for hospitality. The personnel in the waiting area must be reliable and have a score of 6.133. Then FPV 4.8 was the highest expected estimate for the fairness of the price and cost of measuring money. This should have been fair for domestic flights and cost 6.219 points.

Further, HAF 5.5 was the highest-rated subject in hygiene and food measurement. It should be clean and sanitary for roads, streets and parks and score 6.248 points. AAS 6.8 was the most productive in terms of comfort and safety. This is like to try local and western medicine methods and the rating was 6.505. However, these indicators did not differ significantly from other points, indicating that tourists usually expect higher rates from tourism.

In the actual travel experience measurement, the highest value for the real service perceived score item is CTE 1.5. Tourist attractions should include sightseeing and leisure, with a score of 4.990. The highest information measure for the real service perceived item was INF 2.2. It should have been a tourist information Centre, with a score of 4.657. Next, HOS 3.5 is the highest hospitality measurement for an actual item's perceived score item. Staff in the waiting area must be reliable and have a score of 4.505. Then, FPV 4.2 was the highest price and value of money measurement for the real service perceived score item. The cost of living should be reasonable (i.e. for local and foreign tourists), and the score is 5.086. Next, HAF 5.10 measures the highest hygiene and food for the real service perceived score item. The other dish (non-local) is delicious and has a score of 5.190. The AAS 6.1 is the actual service perceived score item in the Facilities and Safety Measurement. It should have good internet connectivity at the hotel and was 5.086 points. There

is little difference in cognitive scores, but usually below expectations. When measuring the main tourist experience, the largest gap indicator was CTE 1.9. It was a tourist environment should be calm and peaceful, and the rating was 1.571. Then, the item “The greatest gaps in the measurement of information” was INF 2.1. It was a tourist information Centre, which should be available at airports, and the rating was 1.610. The next item, “Estimating gaps in the hotel business” was HOS 3.3. The staff at the place of stay should be calm and kind. And dial 1.429. Then, the assessment of the fairness of the price and the cost of the largest gap was equal to FPV 4.6. Tour packages should have a fair value, and the rating was 1.543. Then, the most considerable difference in hygiene and food was HAF 5.5. It is roads, streets and parks that should be clean and sanitary and dial 1.295. In the Convenience and Security category, the most considerable difference in scores was AAS 6.8. like to try local and western medicine methods and the score was 1.724.

Factor Analysis for the Difference between Perceptions and Expectations (Gap Scores) -

Table 6: Factor Analysis (Rotated Component Matrix)

Items	Component							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
HAF 5.3	0.852							
AAS 6.4	0.849							
HAF 5.2	0.842							
HAF 5.1	0.829							
HAF 5.4	0.802		0.405					
AAS 6.6	0.798							
HAF 5.6	0.787							
HAF 5.5	0.777							
AAS 6.5	0.758	0.417						
AAS 6.3	0.743							
AAS 6.2	0.729					0.432		
HAF 5.10	0.727				0.532			
FPV 4.2	0.706	0.428						
FPV 4.4	0.699	0.428	0.453					
AAS 6.8	0.696	0.417						
HAF 5.7	0.692				0.559			
AAS 6.1	0.671							
AAS 6.7	0.668	0.446						
FPV 4.11	0.659					0.436		
FPV 4.3	0.655	0.497	0.421					
FPV 4.10	0.619	0.459						
FPV 4.1	0.618	0.394						
HAF 5.9	0.618				0.669			

HAF 5.8	0.564			0.702	
FPV 4.9	0.561	0.519	0.472		
FPV 4.8	0.552	0.491	0.524		
FPV 4.6	0.467	0.411	0.657		
CTE 1.4	0.430		0.761		
AAS 6.10	0.426	0.439		0.610	
CTE 1.2	0.404		0.497		0.421
CTE 1.3	0.402		0.785		
HOS 3.7		0.837			
HOS 3.8		0.833			
HOS 3.9		0.820			
HOS 3.5		0.789			
HOS 3.10		0.761			
HOS 3.4		0.707	0.443		
HOS 3.3		0.656			0.460
HOS 3.6		0.655		0.415	
HOS 3.2		0.620			0.605
HOS 3.1		0.485			0.661
FPV 4.5		0.410	0.700		
CTE 1.7			0.782		
CTE 1.5			0.727		
CTE 1.6			0.721		
FPV 4.7			0.642		
CTE 1.8			0.533	0.560	
INF 2.2				0.742	
INF 2.3				0.730	
INF 2.1				0.696	
CTE 1.9				0.660	
INF 2.4				0.641	0.491
INF 2.5					0.642
INF 2.6					0.640
AAS 6.9					0.486
CTE 1.1					0.813

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization^a

^aRotation converged in 11 iterations.

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

The factor loadings for each item relative to the different factors are shown in Table 6. These values in the table show the weight and correlation for each item or factor. All values below 0.40 are cut from this table as they are not significant for analysis. Table 4.6 shows that items of

different dimensions are reorganized under the same factor: some items in one dimension are HAF 5.4, AAS 6.5, AAS 6.2, HAF 5.10, AAS 6.7, FPV 4.11, FPV 4.3, FPV 4.10, FPV 4.1, HAF 5.9, HAF 5.8, FPV 4.9, FPV 4.8, FPV 4.6, CTE 1.4, AAS 6.10, CTE 1.2, CTE 1.3, FPV 4.2, FPV 4.4, AAS 6.8, HAF 5.7, HOS 3.4, HOS 3.3, HOS 3.6, HOS 3.2, HOS 3.1 , FPV 4.5, CTE 1.8 and INF 2.4. Analysis of these factors proves that the SERVQUAL model is a good measure of service quality in tourism. This is because the same items were expected to fall under different factors indicating that they measured a different factor.

Description of Measurement and Overall Service Quality -

Table 7: Descriptive statistics for the six dimensions

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
CTE	735	6.11	-1.67	4.44	1.1412	0.05137
INF	735	6.83	-2.5	4.33	1.0635	0.05802
HOS	735	7.2	-2	5.2	1.3229	0.058
FPV	735	6.27	-1.45	4.82	1.1333	0.05284
HAF	735	5.1	-1	4.1	1.0543	0.05506
AAS	735	7.2	-1.2	6	1.3886	0.06391
OSQ	735	5.91	-1.09	4.82	1.184	0.05032
Valid N (listwise)	735					

	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
CTE	1.39279	1.94	0.554	0.09	0.427	0.18
INF	1.57304	2.474	0.085	0.09	-0.127	0.18
HOS	1.57238	2.472	0.135	0.09	-0.056	0.18
FPV	1.43256	2.052	0.495	0.09	0.044	0.18
HAF	1.49284	2.229	0.395	0.09	-0.962	0.18
AAS	1.73259	3.002	0.909	0.09	0.556	0.18
OSQ	1.3641	1.861	0.766	0.09	0.342	0.18

Source: Compiled by the author using data from the survey

Core-tourism experience – CTE

Basic Travel Experience-The average CTE rating is 1.1412 and the average is 6.11. The minimum score is -1.67. The maximum score is 4.44. The standard deviation is 1.392279, which indicates the average interval. The distribution is clearly skewed by the 0.554 curve. This indicates that the

number has shifted to the right. The kurtosis value is 0.427. This means that the cluster is somewhere in the mean.

Information

The average is 1.0635. This means that the tour is satisfied with the quality of service, as can be seen from the reliability side. The standard deviation is 1.57304. This means that the gap moves away from the average. However, unlike the average, the minimum gap is -2.5, and the maximum gap is 4.33. The distribution is skewed at a value of 0.085, the gap is biased to the right of the mean, and the gap is clustered away from the mean with a kurtosis value of -0.127.

Hospitality

Tourists are generally satisfied with the level of service provided by the tourism industry, with a gap of 1.3229 in this indicator. The minimum and maximum are above average, and the gaps are -2 and 5.2, respectively. The standard deviation for debt measurement is 1.57238. This means that the gap is not significantly different from the mean. The deviation is on the right, and the positive curve is 0.135. With a kurtosis value of 0.056, the gaps are clustered at a different location than the mean.

Fairness of price and value of money

The average gap for this measurement is 1.1333, which represents satisfaction. The minimum gap for this measurement is -1.45. The maximum gap is 4.82. The standard deviation is 1.43256, the distribution is skewed at a value of .495, and the gap is collected at some point away from the mean with a kurtosis value of 0.044, so there is little deviation from the mean.

Hygiene and Food

The average gap for hygiene and food measurements is 1.0543. The minimum spacing for this distribution is -1 and the maximum spacing is 4.1. Its standard deviation is 1.49284. This means that the gap is usually different but not much. The distributions are clearly pasted to .0395 and are clustered to the right because the kurtosis values are clustered at a mean of 0.962.

Amenities and Security

This measurement has the smallest gap of 1.3886, indicating the highest measurement that tourists will be happy with. The minimum gap is -1.2, and the maximum gap is 6.0. The standard deviation is 1.73259. This is the measurement with the highest deviation, but it shows a large deviation from the mean. The deviation is on the right because the distribution is skewed at a value of 3.002 and is clustered around values other than the mean. The kurtosis value is 0.556.

Overall Service Quality

Table 7 shows that all tourists are satisfied with their offers. The positive average of 1.184 shows that this exceeds the expectations of the tourism industry. Of all the answers received from respondents, the smallest calculated gap is -1.09, and the largest number of visitors is 4.82. The standard deviations here are much lower than when manipulating the individual dimensions, which show some homogeneity between the populations. The positive, positive value of the distribution is 1.3641, which is further from the mean at some point, so the gap is further offset to the right. The standard deviations of the individual dimensions vary around the general mean and are somewhat consistent around the six dimensions, suggesting different perceptions of quality of service among the surveyed tourists. In summary, the overall perceived quality of service is high (1.184), which means that the level of service they receive is higher than expected. This may be because the tourism industry maintains a complete customer base.

Macro Study - The purpose of analyzing the secondary data collected during the survey is to answer some research questions, as shown in the first chapter, on

- What has happened in world tourism business? Was it declining, or was it increasing?
- What are the most popular destinations for international tourists and inflows?
- What are the minimum destinations for international tourists and inflows?
- How do tourism services and merchandise compare with the payment balance of the destinations in the global?

By answering these questions, it will realize how the world faces these problems.

Global Trend - Figure 4 shows that International tourist arrivals and tourism receipts (% change) from 2008 to 2018.

Except in 2009, there has been an increase in the percentage of international tourists' arrivals and tourism receipts. Despite the occasional shocks, the tourism industry continues to expand over time.

According to available data, international tourist arrivals (night visitors) increased by 5.4% in 2018 compared to in 2017. UNWTO estimates that in 2018, the number of foreign tourists arriving at destinations around the world will reach 1.41 billion, which is about 100 million more than in 2017. This represents the continued 5.4% growth recorded in 2018. The annual average level is 4%. Last 10 years (2008-2018). Growth was driven by the Middle East (+ 8%) and the Asia Pacific

Figure 4: International tourist arrivals and tourism receipts (% change)

Source: Adopted from World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), July 2019.

Figure 5: International tourist arrivals (million) and tourism receipts (USD billion)

Source: Adopted from World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), July 2019.

(+ 6%). International arrivals to Europe (+ 4%) increased on a global average, while there were more modest increases in Africa (+ 3%) and the United States (+ 2%).

A strong economy contributes to the growth of tourism. According to UNWTO, the reasons for this sustainable growth are the following:

- World GDP in 2018 + 3.6%
- Exchange rate fluctuations are generally moderate,

- Low-Interest Rate In international passenger transport,
- IATA measured a fixed passenger kilometre (RPK), fuel prices of + 6% and reduction in fares (-60% fare compared to 1998).
- In the last 20 years, the number of unique cities connected by air traffic has more than doubled, and the cost has exceeded 20,000.
- Artificial Intelligence will transform the tourism industry, and more and more destinations will be able to measure tourism in real-time and manage visitor flows,
- Virtual Assistants to companies that can deliver hyper-personalized customer experience to improve business performance.
- Strengthen visa promotion.

Table 8 shows international tourist arrivals and tourism revenue by the destination country. In addition, table 8 shows more than 1% of international revenue at destinations in 2017. There is a two-way approach. They are the arrivals of international tourists and the revenues of international tourism, 2010, 2017 and 2018 can be compared respectively.

The first is the arrival of international tourists. France was impressive in 2018, with a 6.93% share arriving in France. On the other hand, only 6.42% arrived in Spain, the second most popular destination. France's share in 2017 was 6.66%, which is about 0.39 in Spain and 0.79 in the United States. In 2010, France accounted for 8.21%, and this is the highest figure for this year.

On other hand in term of tourism receipts, year 2010 to year 2018 the United States was the most receipts, more than three times Spain with share of 15.13%. It was the third most popular destination to arrive with 6.17% share in year 2018. The US has over four times more international tourism receipts than France, but proportionally fewer international tourist arrivals at 6.42% share for Spain and 6.93% share for France. As for South Korea, it was least arrival of those given with 1.19% share tourists.

Regional Trend

Figure 4.6 illustrations of international tourist arrivals by region, 2018. The Asia-Pacific region (+ 7%) led to an increase in both arrivals and revenues. In contrast, the Asia-Pacific region recorded the largest increase in arrivals, followed by Africa (+ 7%) Europe recorded + 5%, as well as the Middle East and America, has the lowest rating (+ 2%).

Table 8: International tourist arrivals and tourism receipts by country of destination

Country	International tourist arrivals Share %			International tourism receipts Share %		
	2010	2017	2018	2010	2017	2018*
United States	6.35%	5.90%	6.17%	14.09%	15.74%	15.13%
Spain	5.57%	6.27%	6.42%	5.62%	5.09%	5.20%
France	8.21%	6.66%	6.93%	5.87%	4.53%	4.75%
Thailand	1.69%	2.72%	2.97%	2.07%	4.25%	4.45%
United Kingdom	2.99%	2.88%	2.82%	3.49%	3.66%	3.66%
Italy	4.61%	4.46%	4.82%	3.99%	3.30%	3.48%
Australia	0.62%	0.68%	0.72%	3.35%	3.12%	3.18%
Germany	2.84%	2.87%	3.02%	3.57%	2.97%	3.03%
China	5.89%	4.65%	4.88%	4.71%	2.88%	2.85%
Macao (China)	1.26%	1.32%	1.43%	2.29%	2.66%	2.83%
Japan	0.91%	2.20%	2.42%	1.36%	2.54%	2.90%
Hong Kong (China)	2.12%	2.14%	2.27%	2.28%	2.49%	2.59%
India	0.61%	1.19%	1.35%	1.49%	2.04%	2.02%
Turkey	3.32%	2.88%	3.55%	2.32%	1.68%	1.78%
Mexico	2.46%	3.01%	3.21%	1.23%	1.59%	1.59%
Utd Arab Emirates	0.79%	1.21%	1.23%	0.88%	1.57%	1.51%
Austria	2.33%	2.26%	2.39%	1.91%	1.53%	1.62%
Canada	1.72%	1.60%	1.64%	1.63%	1.52%	1.55%
Singapore	0.97%	1.07%	1.14%	1.46%	1.47%	1.45%
Malaysia	2.60%	1.99%	2.00%	1.86%	1.37%	1.35%
Portugal	0.72%	1.62%	1.77%	1.04%	1.28%	1.38%
Netherlands	1.15%	1.37%	1.47%	1.21%	1.24%	1.32%
Greece	1.59%	2.08%	2.34%	1.31%	1.23%	1.34%
Switzerland	0.91%	0.85%	0.91%	1.51%	1.22%	1.20%
Sweden	0.55%	0.54%	-	0.86%	1.06%	1.06%
Korea (ROK)	0.93%	1.02%	1.19%	1.06%	1.00%	1.08%
Other Countries	36.29%	34.55%	30.94%	27.54%	26.95%	25.71%
	100%	100%	100%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

* Provisional figure

Source: Compiled by the author using World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) www.unwto.org

Figure 6 shows revenues from international tourism by region, 2018 (change in%). According to diagram 7, in the Asia-Pacific region (+ 7%) and Europe (+ 5%), tourism income growth is above average (+ 4%). The Middle East occupies + 4%, as does the average global economic growth. In 2018, Africa received a little slower income from international tourism in the regions. They are marked as +2 per cent and in North and South America +0 per cent.

Figure 6: International tourist arrivals by regions, 2018

Bubble size equivalent to number of international tourist arrivals.

Source: World Tourism Organization (UNWTO).

Figure 7: International tourism receipts by regions, 2018 (% change)

Source: World Tourism Organization (UNWTO)

International tourism exports - According to the UNWTO, in 2018, compared with 2017, export revenues from international tourism (passenger and passenger transportation) increased by USD 121 billion. Export receipts from international tourism are an essential source of foreign income for many destinations in the world. Tourism is an integral part of export diversification for both emerging market economies and developed economies, with great potential to reduce trade deficits and offset lower export income from other goods and services.

Table 9: International tourist arrivals and tourism receipts by region

	International tourist arrivals			International tourism receipts			
	Change %		Share %	USD (Million)			Share %
	17/16	18*/17	2018*	2010	2017	2018*	2018*
Europe	8.6	5.5	100	422,801	519,464	570,463	100
Northern Europe	6	0.5	11.1	60,612	88,571	93,873	17.8
Western Europe	6.1	4	28.2	152,364	170,918	187,474	32.9
Central/Eastern Europe	5.6	5	19.9	48,312	60,684	68,674	12
Southern/Medit. Europe	12.9	8.2	40.8	161,514	199,291	220,443	38.6
Asia and the Pacific	5.7	7.3	100	254,367	395,996	435,460	100
North-East Asia	3.4	6.1	48.7	122,964	168,130	188,429	43.3
South-East Asia	8.8	6.8	37	68,547	130,632	142,314	32.7
Oceania	6.1	2.8	4.9	42,794	57,375	61,097	14
South Asia	6.2	19.4	9.4	20,063	39,858	43,620	10
Americas	4.7	2.3	100	215,538	325,848	333,594	100
North America	4.3	3.7	65.9	164,832	252,409	258,913	77.6
Caribbean	3	-1.4	11.9	23,254	31,802	31,975	9.6
Central America	4.6	-2.4	5	6,947	12,604	12,840	3.8
South America	7.7	1.2	17.2	20,505	29,034	29,865	9
Africa	8.5	7	100	30,447	36,400	38,395	100
North Africa	14.7	10.1	35.5	9,662	9,916	10,674	27.8
Subsaharan Africa	5.5	5.4	64.5	20,785	26,483	27,721	72.2
Middle East	4.1	4.7	100	52,150	68,359	73,039	100

* Provisional figure

Source: Compiled by the author using World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) www.unwto.org

Table 9 illustrates that International tourist arrivals and tourism receipts by region.

Figure 8 shows Tourism Exports and the Balance of Payment Relationship. The tourism industry is generating \$ 5 billion a day for exports. How is this happened ? or Relationship among Tourism export and the balance of payment. Export from international tourism in particular year is equal to receipts in destinations plus passenger transport. International tourism export revenue consists of "travel" (receipt at destination) and "passenger transport" receipt. Both are countries balance of payments credit items. Example in 2018,

Export from international tourism (USD 1.7 trillion) = receipts in destinations (USD 1.5 trillion) + passenger transport (USD 256 billion). Thus , Export from international tourism (USD 1.7 trillion) equal to 7% of global export or 29% of world services export. That's the relationship about Tourism export and the balance of payment.

Figure 8: Relationship between Tourism Exports and the Balance of Payment

Source: Adopted from World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) and World Trade Organization (WTO).

Figure 9 illustrates Export revenues from international tourism and merchandise exports (% change). For the seventh consecutive year (since 2012), the total export revenue of international tourism grew faster than the export of goods. As example in 2018, Merchandise exports (% change) ranked + 3% however, International tourism exports (% change, real terms) would be + 4%.

Figure 9: Export revenues from international tourism and merchandise exports (% change)

Source: Adopted from World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) and World Trade Organization (WTO).

Ten top destinations performance - Figure 10 illustrates the top ten destinations in arrivals, and in 2018 they received 40% of international visitors. All other destinations grew in 2018, except the UK.

Figure 10: Top ten destinations by international tourist arrivals, 2018

Source: Adopted from World Tourism Organization (UNWTO).

Figure 11 illustrates the top ten destinations by international tourism receipts and in 2018 they accounted for almost 50% of all international tourism income. All other areas grew in 2018, China became the highest rating, it amounted to 40 billion US dollars. The highest income country for arriving in Luxembourg, followed by Australia, earning about USD 4,900 for international arrivals.

Figure 9 and Table 10 show the ten most popular destinations for international tourism receipts in 2017. According to Figure 9 and table 10, with the exception of 2015, all other changes in tourism exports increased from 2010 to 2018. However, in 2015 and 2016 the change in exports of goods decreased, and other years grew in it. According to Figure 9 and Table 10, International Tourism, revenues (% of total exports) have steadily increased from 16.55% to 17.71% for all years.

Figure 11: Top ten destinations by international tourism receipts, 2018

Source: Adopted from World Tourism Organization (UNWTO).

Figure 9: Top Ten Destinations Performance

Source: Compiled by the author using World Development Indications

Table 10: Top Ten Destinations Performance

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Change in Tourism Exports	11.14 %	16.22 %	2.51 %	8.77 %	2.18 %	- 3.99 %	1.41 %	7.50 %	7.30 %
Change in Merchandise exports	16.71 %	16.90 %	0.34 %	5.03 %	1.33 %	- 8.96 %	- 2.26 %	9.90 %	8.66 %
International tourism, receipts (% of total exports)	16.55 %	16.55 %	16.63 %	16.98 %	16.96 %	17.46 %	17.73 %	17.71 %	17.56 %

Source: Compiled by the author using World Development Indications

Conclusion

Sri Lanka is beautiful island nation. The tourism industry is growing industry in there. President Gotabaya Rajapaksha 1st the policy statement in parliament at 2020-01-03 said that *“Tourism industry is one of the most important sectors in our economy to generate foreign exchange earnings. It is also an area that could be easily developed. Our aim is to annually add a foreign exchange inflow of USD 10 billion to the domestic economy from tourism”*.

Likewise, in the world economy, international tourism is ahead of other industries and services. According to UNWTO, the number of foreign tourists in 2018 increased by 5%, due to the relatively strong global economy, the growth of the middle class in countries with developing economies, technological advances, new business models, affordable travel expenses and visa facilitation 1.4 billion reached. At the same time, export revenue from tourism increased to 1.7 trillion. This makes the sector a truly global force for economic growth and development, stimulates the creation of new and better jobs and serves as a catalyst for innovation and entrepreneurship. In short, tourism helps millions of people build a better life and transform the whole of society.

Nevertheless, the truth may differ from expectations. Therefore, this study conducted a survey based on the SERVQUAL model. Thus, the research questions are as follows: What things maximize the level of tourist satisfaction? How do customers guarantee travel providers? This article directly addresses the main purpose of this document to study the impact of tourism expectations and perceptions on the services provided by the global tourism industry.

Meanwhile, other research questions; What happened in the global tourism business? Was it decreasing, or was it increasing? What are the most popular destinations for foreign tourists and tributaries? What are the minimum destinations for foreign tourists and tributaries? How do

tourism services and goods compare with the balance of payments of the ten most popular destinations? Are a target for other specific purposes. There are to explore the world tourism business, whether it is decreasing or increasing, analyze the most popular destinations and the smallest destinations for international tourists and tributaries, analyze regional tourism for international tourists and tributaries and compare travel services and trade in goods, analyzing the Balance of payments for the ten most popular destinations.

In the methodology part, the research divided into two parts. First one is micro study and second is macro study. The micro study, the researchers conducted a survey based on the SERVQUAL model. After SPSS software, the research exam reliability and validity testing, a summary of the means of customer expectations and gap scores, factor analysis of the differences between perceptions and expectations, measurement explanations and overall quality of service. The macro study of the research was deliberated UNWTO report.

The study used SERVQUAL models for skiing (Fick & Ritchie, 1991), winter resorts (Weiermair & Fuchs, 1999), rural tourism (Reichel et al., 2000), theme parks (O'Neill, 2000) or entire destinations. (Chaudhary, 2000; Edward, 2006; Tribe & Snaith, 1998). It appears that the scale has been tested in various subsectors of tourism services such as the airlines (Fick & Ritchie, 1991; Otto & Ritchie, 1996), hotels (Fick & Ritchie, 1991; Otto & Ritchie, 1996) and tourist attractions. (Otto & Ritchie, 1996) and travel agency (Millan & Esteban, 2004). This aspect leads to the fact that tourism is essentially an industrial synthesis (Otto & Ritchie, 1996). It is a complex network of aviation, hospitality, tourism and travel, sightseeing, entertainment and shopping, where community participation and overall government coordination are key factors. The latter type of research seems to pay limited attention to the type of attractiveness that the destination offers. In such cases, the scale covers the range from culture to contamination, so the measurement range seems to be more complete. This may be a flaw in the study, but according to the problem, general questions in the study are accepted.

Next thing is how research questions responded to the research objectives. The first main question, what kind of things do maximum in the tourists' satisfaction level? The overall perceived quality of service is high (1.184), which means that the level of service they receive is higher than expected. This may be because the tourism industry maintains a complete customer base. Second questions, how are the customers guarantee on tourist service providers? In the survey, Information and Hospitality are leading this question. Gap scores of Information have rated 0.705 to 1.610, and

Hospitality has recorded 1.162 to 1.429. That is tourist service providers has guaranteed in this survey. Therefore, the impact of tourism expectations and perception on services provided by the world's tourism industry is accomplished by in the research.

So, another question is what's happening in global tourism? According to available data, international tourist arrivals (night visitors) increased by 5.4% in 2018 compared to 2017. The UNWTO told that in 2018, the number of foreign tourists arriving at destinations around the world reached 1,410 million. That's more than in 2017. It is the world's world tourism industry. Another sub question is was the world tourism industry declining or growing? This represents a continuous 5.4% growth recorded in 2018. The average annual level for the last 10 years (2008-2018) is 4%. Growth was driven by the Middle East (+8%) and the Asia Pacific (+6%). International arrivals to Europe (+4%) increased on a global average, with modest increases in Africa (+3%) and the United States (+2%). As such, world travel and tourism are undoubtedly increasing in the global area.

Next, question is what are the most popular destinations for international tourists and inflows? The first is the arrival of international tourists. France was impressive in 2018, with a 6.93% share arriving in France. On the other hand, only 6.42% arrived in Spain, the second most popular destination. France's share in 2017 was 6.66%, which is about 0.39 in Spain and 0.79 in the United States. In 2010, France accounted for 8.21%, and this is the highest figure for this year. On other hand in term of tourism receipts, year 2010 to year 2018 the United States was the most receipts, more than three times Spain with share of 15.13%. It was the third most popular destination to arrive with 6.17% share in year 2018. The US has over four times more international tourism receipts than France, but proportionally fewer international tourist arrivals at 6.42% share for Spain and 6.93% share for France. As for South Korea, it was least arrival of those given with 1.19% share tourists. The Asia-Pacific region (+ 7%) led to an increase in both arrivals and revenues. In contrast, the Asia-Pacific region recorded the largest increase in arrivals, followed by Africa (+ 7%) Europe recorded + 5%, as well as the Middle East and America, has the lowest rating (+ 2%). In the Asia-Pacific region (+ 7%) and Europe (+ 5%), tourism income growth is above average (+ 4%). The Middle East occupies + 4%, as does the average global economic growth. In 2018, Africa received a little slower income from international tourism in the regions. They are marked as +2 per cent and in North and South America +0 per cent. Next questions are what are the minimum destinations for international tourists and inflows? Fifty countries including Comoros, Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Eritrea, Gabon, Liberia, Somalia, Libya, Syria and Yemen have less than 1,000

international tourist and have not recorded international receipts. Andorra and Guam countries have less than 4,000 international tourist and have not recorded international receipts. Hence, analyses regional tourism for international tourists and inflows are completed.

Final question is how do tourism services and merchandise compare with the payment balance of the destinations in global? Export from international tourism (USD 1.7 trillion) = receipts in destinations (USD 1.5 trillion) + passenger transport (USD 256 billion). Thus, Export from international tourism (USD 1.7 trillion) equal to 7% of global export or 29% of world services export. That's the relationship about Tourism export and the balance of payment.

It is notable concept that According to micro study, most tourists came from China. This was 12.8%. The second place went to the USA, and it was 7.07%. 3rd place went to France, and it amounted to 5.44%. According to UNWTO, it is recorded First place China, Second place United States of America, third place Germany, forth place UK and fifth place France. In the Micro study of the most visited destinations in France, it was 8.98%. Spain took second place, and it amounted to 8.47%. The USA took 3rd place, and it amounted to 7.95% and macro study most popular destinations are France, Spain, United States, China, Italy, Turkey, Mexico, Germany, Thailand and United Kingdom in this research.

Conclusion - The main purpose of the study is to investigate the impact of tourism expectations and perceptions on the services offered by the global tourism industry. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the main goals were successfully achieved, and other specific tasks were included in the study. The SERVQUAL model is used in this research. Even so, the SERVQUAL model must be transformed in such a way that it can gather the perspectives and understandings of research and tourism. Macro study is value added to the research. Finally, even though tourism satisfaction is the focus of the micro-foundations, the addition of macro studies to this study is more significant.

Policy Recommendation - Based on the findings of the micro study, the recommendations outlined in this article are expected to brighten the international tourism industry. Health tourism should be increased, and a mechanism to meet the demand of tourists for indigenous and traditional therapies other than Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani and western medicine will be focused. Tourism Security must be concerned about every nation. Therefore, the World Tourism Organization should do a proper mechanism to tourist safety.

In the macro study western countries more dominated international tourist arrivals and international tourism receipts. Fifty nations who have less than thousands international tourists' arrivals and no proper recording international tourism receipts. This should be changed. Future research is encouraged to explore larger sample sizes and different industries using input-output methods, gravity models, computable general equilibrium (CGE) models, and partial equilibrium models.

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Finding

Reliability and Validity are ok and Factor analysis is ok

The overall perceived quality of service is high

75 % of International tourism arrival and International tourism receipts are western countries

Export from international tourism (USD 1.7 trillion) equal to 7% of global export or 29% of world services export

Discussion

1. What kind of things do maximum in the tourists' satisfaction level?
2. How are the customers guarantee on tourist service providers?
3. What has happened in world tourism business? Was it declining, or was it increasing?
4. What are the most popular destinations for international tourists and inflows?
5. What are the minimum destinations for international tourists and inflows?
6. How do tourism services and merchandise compare with the payment balance of the destinations in the global? Are successfully addressed

Conclusion

Finally, even though tourism satisfaction is the focus of the micro-foundations, the addition of macro studies to this study is more significant.

Recommendation

Health tourism and Tourism Security must be addressed
75 % of International tourism arrival and International tourism receipts are western countries must be changed

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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